

Toward transitioning to green and sustainable supercapacitors

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Supercapacitor
Green solvents
Cyrene
Tamisolve
NMP
Nitrogen-doped graphene

ABSTRACT

The rapid advancement of supercapacitor technologies has intensified the demand for sustainable electrode fabrication methods that minimize environmental impact. A major challenge arises from the extensive use of the toxic solvent *N*-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP), which is subject to increasingly stringent regulatory restrictions. We demonstrate that NMP can be effectively replaced with two green solvents, dihydrolevoglucosenone (Cyrene) and *N*-butyl-2-pyrrolidone (Tamisolve), without compromising electrochemical performance. Electrode formulations were prepared using nitrogen-doped graphene as the active material, in combination with either polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF), a widely employed fluorinated binder, or polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP), a non-fluorinated alternative with improved environmental profile. Optimized coatings exhibited high mass loadings exceeding 6 mg cm^{-2} while maintaining strong adhesion to current collectors, an often overlooked yet critical parameter for scalable manufacturing. Electrochemical testing revealed that PVDF in Cyrene delivered an energy density of 66.6 Wh kg^{-1} at a power density of 1.85 kW kg^{-1} , with excellent cycling stability, retaining 91 % of capacitance after 100,000 cycles. PVP in Cyrene provided a more environmentally benign alternative, achieving an energy density of 64.2 Wh kg^{-1} at 1.80 kW kg^{-1} , with 78 % capacitance retention after 100,000 cycles, thereby highlighting the trade-off between performance and sustainability.

1. Introduction

Supercapacitors are increasingly recognized as rapidly evolving components in the landscape of electrochemical energy storage, offering unparalleled power density, ultrafast charging, and exceptional cycle life. Their potential spans a wide spectrum of applications, which range from micro-mobility and industrial electronics to aerospace and renewable energy systems, i.e., domains where rapid and reliable energy delivery is crucial [1]. Despite these advantages, the widespread adoption of supercapacitors is constrained by the need to balance electrochemical performance with environmental sustainability and manufacturing scalability [2]. The development of next-generation electrode materials and processing technologies, particularly considering emerging regulations on hazardous substances such as *N*-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP), represents an important challenge. In

supercapacitor electrode processing, NMP is a highly effective solvent for dispersing carbon-based active materials, enabling the formation of homogeneous slurries and well-stacked electrode films. However, NMP is classified as a toxic substance, labeled by the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency as a developmental toxicant [3] and recognized in the European Union as a reproductive toxin, falling under the category of a Substance of Very High Concern (SVHC) [4,5]. These drawbacks drive research for safer and more sustainable solvent alternatives, but no single alternative solvent matches the performance of NMP.

Electrode processing technologies based on aqueous environments are particularly attractive as they offer a green alternative to NMP, but their deployment is challenging due to the identification of suitable water-soluble binders with high thermal stability and strong adhesion [6–8]. In parallel, various nontoxic organic solvents have been investigated for slurry preparation [9]. Among these dimethyl sulfoxide

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2025.172220>

Received 30 August 2025; Received in revised form 23 November 2025; Accepted 22 December 2025

Available online 23 December 2025

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(DMSO) [10–12], green solvents such as γ -valerolactone (GVL) [13,14] – brand name Cyrene (Cy) [15,16] were very rarely tested in the context of supercapacitors, N-butyl-2-pyrrolidone – brand name Tamisolve (Tam), remains unexplored. GVL, derived from cellulosic biomass and commonly used in organic synthesis, dissolves PVDF only at elevated temperatures. While Cyrene has demonstrated the ability to support graphene dispersions of comparable quality to those prepared in NMP [17,18], its high surface tension and viscosity hinder wettability and adhesion, often leading to delamination from bare aluminum substrates in Li-ion battery applications [19]. Additionally, Cyrene exhibits limited solubility for PVDF, and although elevated temperatures (e.g., 90 °C) can partially improve its performance, this complicates the coating process and may reduce scalability. Also, OECD and GHS assessments classify Cyrene as non-mutagenic, environmentally benign, and readily biodegradable [15,20,21].

One of the key challenges in adopting new solvents is achieving the same electrode cohesion and adhesion to the current collector as for NMP-based slurries. PVDF in NMP provides good adhesion and mechanical strength after drying, whereas slurries prepared with GVL or Cyrene face challenges related to suboptimal adhesion of the deposited film to the electrode surface. In the field of Li-ion batteries, where the fabrication of cathodes faces similar challenges, a modification of the electrode surface by plasma and chemical etching improved the electrode wettability, which significantly improved the adhesion of Cyrene-based coatings [22]. Evaluation of electrode adhesion to the substrate and the occurrence of cracking are often overlooked in scientific publications, despite their critical role for moving from laboratory-scale processes to electrode fabrication. Considering the emerging regulatory pressures and environmental concerns about NMP, this study explores Cyrene and Tamisolve as greener solvent alternatives for fabricating supercapacitor electrodes. Their low toxicity and biodegradability make them sustainable alternatives and the basis for their selection [15,23–25]. While Cyrene has been successfully utilized as a solvent in the fabrication of battery electrodes, its use in supercapacitor slurries is rare [16,26]. The studies [17,22] showed only a limited evaluation of Cyrene-processed electrodes, with low mass loading, short cycling, and no adhesion testing. Here, we demonstrate industrially relevant mass loadings, high mechanical robustness, and 100,000 cycling stability at 10 A g⁻¹.

Tamisolve, on the other hand, has not yet been utilized as a solvent. We also compare PVDF, the standard fluorinated binder, with PVP, a more environmentally benign non-fluorinated alternative. Combining strong adhesion with high mass loading remains difficult, especially for new nanomaterials with low-binder content [27–31].

This study represents the first demonstration of SC-GN3 processed using Cyrene and Tamisolve as green solvents. It also introduces the first example of high mass-loading electrodes prepared with a fully green solvent–binder system. Electrodes with a high mass loading (>6 mg cm⁻²) were fabricated and evaluated for mechanical robustness, focusing on adhesion and flexibility, two critical parameters for scalable electrode manufacturing [32]. Electrodes processed with Cyrene and Tamisolve showed superior mechanical integrity compared to NMP-based counterparts, while retaining comparable electrochemical performance. Replacing PVDF with PVP had minimal impact on capacitance, reinforcing its promise as a viable green binder, however, a capacitance retention dropped. However, the lower capacitance and retention reflect a balance between performance and environmental sustainability. Altogether, this work presents a practical route toward more sustainable electrode processing and offers a transferable framework for greener manufacturing across a broad range of electrochemical energy storage technologies.

2. Experimental

2.1. Reagents and materials

Graphite fluoride (>61 wt% F), NaN₃ (ReagentPlus, ≥99.5 %), Dimethylformamide (DMF), Acetonitrile, Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) K30 (M.W. ~40,000), Cyrene (Dihydrolevoglucosenone), 1-Ethyl-3-methylimidazolium tetrafluoroborate ([EMIM][BF₄]) was purchased from Merck, Poly(vinylidene fluoride) (PVDF) Solef® 5130 was purchased from Solvay, Tamisolve (n-butyl-2-pyrrolidone) was purchased from Carl Roth, 1,1,2,2-Tetrafluoroethyl-2,2,3,3-tetrafluoropropyl (TTE) was purchased from TCI. Acetone and Ethanol were purchased from Lachema. Tetraethylammonium tetrafluoroborate ([TEA][BF₄]), Timcal Super C45 (TC) (Imerys, BET 60 m² g⁻¹, particle size ~50 nm, Figs. S1, S2.), and aluminum foil coated by porous carbon (C-Al-foil) were purchased from Cambridge Energy Solutions. Membra-cell® MD44 dialysis membranes were used for dialysis. Ultrapure water (18 M Ω cm⁻¹) was used for washings and dialysis. Cutter for grid test CC3000 by ISO standard 2409 purchased from Proinex Instruments s.r.o. Adhesive tapes were purchased from 3 M.

2.2. Synthesis of the active material

A nitrogen-doped graphene derivative (SC-GN3) was obtained using the large-scale synthesis (100 g) based on the procedure reported previously [33]. Shortly, a graphite fluoride (125 g, >61 wt% F, Merck) was dispersed in 4.8 L of *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF, ≥98 %, Merck) and stirred for four days. Sodium azide (250 g, BioXtra, Merck) was then gradually added, and the mixture was heated at 130 °C for 72 h with continuous stirring. After cooling, the product was washed sequentially with 3 L of each solvent: DMF, acetone, ethanol, hot water, water, and acidified water (3 % HCl), followed by separation through filtration.

2.3. Fabrication of electrodes

Electrodes were fabricated using a consistent composition: 87 wt% SC-GN3 (active material), 3 wt% binder (either PVDF or PVP), and 10 wt % TC (as a conductive additive). First, the binder was dissolved in the solvent. PVDF was dissolved in NMP or Tamisolve by mixing overnight at laboratory temperature and sonicated at 50 °C for 1 h. PVDF was dissolved in Cyrene by mixing overnight at laboratory temperature. After that, it was heated up to 100 °C for 30 min and sonicated at 50 °C for 1 h. PVP was dissolved in the solvent (NMP, Cyrene, or Tamisolve) by mixing overnight at the laboratory temperature. Next, the dissolved binder and TC were vortex-mixed; subsequently, SC-GN3, serving as the active material, was added. The quantities of components used were 222.5 mg of SC-GN3, 7.5 mg of PVP or PVDF, 25 mg of Timcal and 845 μ L of NMP, Cyrene, or Tamisolve. The mixture was vortex-mixed for 1 min and then mixed for 10 min in a planetary mixer (1100 rpm, Thinky Inc.). The resulting mixture was sonicated for 1 h at 50 °C and was further mixed for 10 min in the planetary mixer to achieve a paste-like consistency.

The paste-like slurry was coated onto C-Al-foil using a doctor blade technique and dried in a vacuum oven (120 °C, 12 h). The electrode films were calendared to consolidate the material layers, and 18 mm discs were subsequently cut from the foils. These discs were then further dried in a flask under vacuum at an elevated temperature (120 °C) for 5 h before being used as electrodes in a 2-electrode setup. The mass loading (including active material, the binder and TC) was maintained between 15.8 and 18 mg per electrode (corresponding to the range of 6.2–7.1 mg cm⁻²).

2.4. Supercapacitor assembly

To assemble the supercapacitor device for testing, two electrodes were placed into the El-Cell insulator sleeves with a separator

(Whatman® glass microfiber, 0.26 mm thick). 140 μL of electrolyte was dropped onto the separator. The electrodes were then enclosed and compressed within the sleeve using stainless steel plungers (height number 200). The entire device was tightened and connected to the PAT-cell docking station. Prior to conducting actual material testing, conditioning was carried out as described in SI.

The specific capacitance of the active material (C_s , F g^{-1}) was calculated from the GCD discharge curve according to eq. (1):

$$C_s = 4 \frac{I \times \Delta t}{m \times \Delta V} \quad (1)$$

Where C_s is the gravimetric capacitance (F g^{-1}), I is the applied discharge current (A), Δt is the discharge time (s), ΔV is the potential window, and m is the total mass of active electrode material (SC-GN3, TC, binder) on both electrodes, therefore the $\frac{I}{m}$ is the current density for the material cast on the current collector. A multiplier of 4 corrects the capacitance of the cell and the combined mass of two electrodes to the metrics of a capacitance and mass of a single electrode [34].

Energy density (Wh kg^{-1}) was calculated according to the formula (2):

$$E = \frac{1}{2} \frac{C_s \times \Delta V^2}{4 \times 3.6} \quad (2)$$

Where C_s is the gravimetric capacitance, ΔV is the operating window, and the dividing factor of 4 is used to normalize the results back to the values of the full-cell setup. A numerical factor of 3.6 was used to convert the energy value to Wh.

Power density (W kg^{-1}) was calculated according to the formula (3):

$$P = \frac{E \times 3.6}{\Delta t} \quad (3)$$

Where E is calculated energy density and Δt is the discharging time.

Equivalent series resistance (ESR) (Ω) was calculated from the GCD discharge curve according to eq. (4):

$$ESR = \frac{(\Delta V_{max} - \Delta V_{drop}) \times 1000}{m} \quad (4)$$

Where ΔV_{max} is maximum potential and ΔV_{drop} is potential after IR drop, and m is the total of active material on both electrodes. The factor 1000 accounts for converting the electrode mass from grams to kilograms when calculating ESR.

2.5. Characterization techniques

For the solubility experiments, 1 wt% solutions of PVDF or PVP in each solvent were prepared. PVDF or PVP was dissolved in NMP, Cyrene or Tamisolve by mixing overnight at laboratory temperature, sonicated at 65 °C for 1 h. PVDF-Cyrene (PVDF-Cy) solution was also prepared using an alternative procedure, as it did not dissolve well in Cyrene under these conditions. The PVDF-Cy mixture was stirred overnight at room temperature, then heated to 100 °C for 30 min, and subsequently sonicated at 65 °C for one hour.

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) analysis was carried out using a Nexsa G2 spectrometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific) equipped with an Al $K\alpha$ radiation source. The data obtained were analyzed using Avantage software, and the spectra were referenced to a carbon C—C peak at 284.8 eV. The sample morphology was examined using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) JEOL 7900F microscope (JEOL, Japan), with an accelerating voltage of 5 kV.

High-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HR-TEM) was performed using a FEI TITAN G2 60–300 HRTEM microscope. The microscope was equipped with an X-FEG emission gun operating at 300 kV, and an objective-lens spherical aberration corrector.

Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectra were recorded using an iS5

FTIR spectrometer (Thermo Nicolet) equipped with a Smart Orbit ATR accessory containing a ZnSe crystal. Raman spectra were acquired using a DXR Raman microscope with a 633 nm excitation diode laser. Galvanostatic charge-discharge (GCD), cyclic voltammetry (CV), and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) were performed on a Bio-Loginstrument (BCS-810) controlled with the BT-Lab software (version 1.75). For evaluation of the two-electrode system, a symmetrical full-cell supercapacitor device was assembled to analyze the performance of the electrodes.

The electrolyte was formulated as a mixture of two solvents to leverage the distinct advantages of both ionic liquids and organic solvents. One half of the electrolyte consisted of a mixture of [EMIM][BF₄] and TTE in a 9:1 volume ratio. The other half was composed of [TEA][BF₄] dissolved in propylene carbonate. [EMIM][BF₄] and TTE were dried for two weeks and PC for one week using 4 Å molecular sieves at room temperature in the glovebox and separately. Then, the final electrolyte was mixed and well stirred before use. [TEA][BF₄] salt was dried at 90 °C for 15 min. The ionic conductivity of the electrolyte was determined to be $2.01 \pm 0.04 \text{ mS cm}^{-1}$ and viscosity was assessed to be 11.0 mPa s, both methods are described in detail in the SI (Fig. S3).

The grid test was conducted by a certified cutter with the ISO 2409 standard, and peeling film off was done by adhesive tapes with defined adhesion. Tapes were used on every sample in same order as follows: 0.8 N cm^{-1} , 1.15 N cm^{-1} , 2.6 N cm^{-1} , 10.6 N cm^{-1} .

3. Results and discussion

Material Synthesis and Characterization.

In this work, we used SC-GN3 from scaled-up synthesis based on a 100 g batch, based on a previously published protocol [33]. As properties of SC-GN3 prepared via scaled-up process may differ from those obtained in laboratory, the material underwent rigorous quality control, confirming its high nitrogen content of up to 16.2 at.% as determined by XPS (Fig. 1a). Detailed analysis of C 1 s HR-XPS spectra (Fig. 1b) revealed aromatic sp^2 carbons at 284.8 eV (53 %). Nitrogen-bonded carbons appeared in both pyridinic and pyrrolic forms, respectively, with minor contributions from oxygen functionality and residual bonded fluorine, and the edge $-\text{CF}_x$ moieties. The high nitrogen doping and surface functionalities of SC-GN3 increase its surface charge and improve wettability. These features, combined with the polarity of the solvents, yield highly stable dispersions [35,36].

The Fig. 1c (and Figs. S4, S5) show the 2D morphology of SC-GN3 sheets used for electrodes, confirming the multilayer graphene structure. SC-GN3 exhibited aromatic-ring vibrations, observed at 1400 cm^{-1} , coming from a heteroatom substitution, e.g., pyridinic nitrogens (Fig. 1d, S6) [37,38]. Moreover, the 1560 cm^{-1} and $\sim 1177 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ bands signify the emergence of the aromatic, conductive carbon network, which is highly beneficial for further use of the material in an electrochemical application [37]. The Raman spectrum of SC-GN3 (Fig. 1e) displayed broad D and G bands at 1350 and 1590 cm^{-1} , respectively, with an I_D/I_G ratio of 1.09 (Fig. 1e), indicating a large number of defects. All these features agree well with the previously published results [33].

3.1. Solvent and binder evaluation

The choice of Cyrene and Tamisolve was driven by the growing need for more sustainable processing methods, with low toxicity and reduced environmental impact. NMP was replaced with Cyrene and Tamisolve as greener processing solvents for slurry preparation, with their key properties summarized in Table 1. Important properties of all three solvents are summarized in Table 1.

The solubility of the binders PVDF and PVP was assessed by dissolving them in each of the three solvents under the same conditions, i.e. stirring overnight and sonication at 65 °C for 1 h (Fig. 2a). NMP exhibited excellent solubility for both PVDF and PVP. In contrast, Cyrene demonstrated poor solubility for PVDF under these conditions.

Fig. 1. (a) XPS Survey spectrum of SC-GN3. (b) Deconvolution of the XPS spectrum for the C1s regions of SC-GN3. (c) SEM image of SC-GN3 particle. (d) FTIR spectrum of SC-GN3. (e) Raman spectrum of SC-GN3.

Table 1

Comparison of selected properties of tested solvents.

Solvent	Boiling point (°C)	Surface tension (mN m ⁻¹ at 25 °C)	Viscosity at 25 °C (mPa s)	Flash point (°C)	Price (EUR/L)*	Application challenges
NMP	202	41	1.7	91	49	Toxic, hazardous, and usage restrictions
Cyrene	226	72.5	15	108	317	Poor adhesion, solvability issues with PVDF
Tamisolve	241	67.3	4	108	79	No data available

* price quotation per 1 L volumes from Carl Roth (6/2025).

Fig. 2. (a) Solubility of binders in solvents. From left: PVP or PVDF in NMP, PVP or PVDF in Cyrene, PVP or PVDF in Tamisolve. (b) Structural formula of NMP, Cyrene and Tamisolve solvents. (c) Photographs of dried binder films on a glass slide. (d) Dispersion of SC-GN3 in NMP, Cyrene, Tamisolve, Acetone, and ACN before and after 4 h, showing sedimentation in Acetone and ACN solutions.

To overcome that, PVDF-Cy mixture was prepared similarly but heated to 100 °C prior to the sonication step, which resulted in complete dissolution of PVDF (Fig. S7). This behavior is attributed primarily to the high molecular weight (1.1 MDa) of the used PVDF. While such high molecular weight PVDF promotes strong adhesion in cathode fabrication on bare aluminum, it also makes achieving complete dissolution of the polymer in Cyrene more difficult. Cyrene exhibited good solubility

for PVP, while Tamisolve showed excellent solubility for PVP and also good solubility for PVDF (only partial opacity). PVDF was completely dissolved in Tamisolve at an elevated temperature (65 °C) and 21 h of sonication in a sonication bath, while no significant dissolution was observed in Cyrene (Fig. S7). Subsequently, the binder solutions were cast onto glass slides and dried (Fig. 2c). PVDF-NMP film exhibited a pronounced coffee-ring effect, with pores in the middle, resulting in

uneven distribution of the binder. A similar effect was observed for PVDF dissolved in Cyrene. Notably, PVDF dissolved in Tamisolve produced a uniform, homogeneous film without signs of phase separation. In comparison, PVP consistently formed transparent, well-distributed films from all solvents (Fig. 2c). Binary mixtures of SC-GN3 with NMP, Cyrene, and Tamisolve were prepared, where SC-GN3 formed long-lasting, stable dispersions in all three solvents, with no significant agglomeration or sedimentation observed over a time of 4 h. (Fig. 2d). To compare, the particles visibly sedimented in Acetonitrile (ACN) and acetone (Fig. 2d) after 4 h.

3.2. Electrochemical performance evaluation

Electrochemical evaluations of electrodes fabricated with various binders and solvents revealed significant differences among individual binders in electrochemical performance (Table 2, Fig. 3a-d). Traditionally, PVDF combined with NMP serves as the standard binder-solvent pair in supercapacitors. With this combination, we achieved a gravimetric capacitance of 131 F g⁻¹ at 1 A g⁻¹ in a 2-electrode setup. We further investigated Cyrene and Tamisolve as non-toxic alternatives to NMP for electrode fabrication. The PVDF-Cy exhibited superior performance, achieving a specific capacitance of 152 F g⁻¹ and the lowest ESR of 7.1 Ω, surpassing the traditional PVDF-NMP system, while maintaining a high mass loading (>6 mg cm⁻²) and outperforming other supercapacitors in the field [39–41]. The PVDF-Tam exhibited 140 F g⁻¹ at 1 A g⁻¹ and an ESR of 10.2 Ω. The GCD curves (Fig. 3a) displayed the characteristic triangular shape of electric double-layer capacitors (EDLCs), with a small IR drop of ≈0.26 V. The slight IR drop likely originates from the contact resistance at the electrode-current collector interface, further enhanced by thick, high-mass electrodes with limited ion diffusion at higher current densities. The CV profiles (Fig. 3b) exhibit distorted rectangular voltammograms, attributed to high mass loading and fast scan rates, indicating predominant EDLC behavior with no significant redox peaks. This suggests a highly reversible process, well-suited for long-term stability. In our high-mass-loading electrodes, pseudocapacitance, often observed in nitrogen-doped systems, is not present in our CV curves [33]. As the conditions required for fast, reversible surface redox reactions are not fully met. Increased electrode thickness can limit ion transport, reduce accessible surface area, and create regions that are effectively inactive for pseudocapacitive reactions [41,42]. Coulombic efficiency remained consistently at 100 % for all samples (Fig. 3c), while long-term cyclic stability was sustained across a wide potential window of 3.7 V (100,000 cycles), still preserving high energy density at 10 A g⁻¹ (Fig. 3d, S8).

Capacitance retention after 100,000 cycles (10 A g⁻¹) was 82 % for PVDF-Tam and 91 % for PVDF-Cy, highlighting their durability. The PVDF-Cy system delivered an energy density of 66.6 Wh kg⁻¹ with a power density of 1.85 kW kg⁻¹ at 1 A g⁻¹. EIS results, presented as Nyquist plots in the inset of Fig. 3c, showed minuscule semicircles in the high-frequency region, indicating minimal Faradaic reactions and

Table 2

The effect of solvent and binder combination on gravimetric capacitance. The capacitance was calculated from GCD cycle recorded at the current density of 1 A g⁻¹.

Mixture	Binder	Solvent	Capacitance in two-electrode setup (F g ⁻¹)	Total mass loading (mg)	Mass loading (mg cm ⁻²)	ESR (Ω)
87 % SC-GN3 +	PVDF	NMP	131	32.6	6.4	9.8
3 % binder	PVDF	Cyrene	152	31.5	6.2	6.9
	PVDF	Tamisolve	140	31.6	6.2	10.2
	PVP	NMP	117	36.2	7.1	7.9
	PVP	Cyrene	133	32.7	6.4	7.1
10 % Timcal	PVP	Tamisolve	–	–	–	–

confirming the predominance of EDLC behavior. This suggests a rapid electron transfer at the electrolyte/electrode interface, with low ESR ranging from 6.9 to 10.2 Ω, which indicates a sufficient accessibility of ions to active sites. The steep incline signifies low resistivity and good capacitive properties with good ion diffusion (equivalent circuit used for fit is depicted in Fig. S9) [43]. Self-discharge, leakage current and stability hold test were also performed (Fig. S10), showing that the final device configuration is far more influential on these values than the active material or slurry composition (rate perf. tests in Fig. S11). Seeking environmentally friendly alternatives, we transitioned to PVP as a more environmentally benign non-fluorinated binder. The PVP-Cy combination delivered a comparable capacitance of 133 F g⁻¹, as evidenced by the GCD curves in Fig. 3a. Consequently, the PVP-Cy electrode achieved an energy density of 64.2 Wh kg⁻¹ and a power density of 1.80 kW kg⁻¹ at 1 A g⁻¹, with 78 % capacitance retention after 100,000 cycles. Notably, the cycling performance of the PVP binder electrodes was lower than those with the PVDF binder. This could be caused by the interaction of the binder with one of the electrolyte components under the applied 3.7 V potential window, or by the hydrophilic nature of PVP. PVP adsorbs water even from trace amounts. Although the electrodes were dried prior to assembly and assembly was done in a glovebox under inert and dry conditions, potential adsorbed moisture cannot be fully excluded. Residual water may trigger electrolyte decomposition, which could cause reduced cycling stability. The PVP-Tam film peeled off the substrate, and although we performed several trials with varying drying temperatures, the film did not remain on the surface and was not measurable for electrochemical analysis.

3.3. Mechanical flexibility and adhesion tests

Bending tests around a steel rod with a 180° bending radius (Fig. 4a-e) were performed to evaluate mechanical flexibility, structural integrity, and endurance of the electrode against peeling from the current collector, which is a significant parameter during the process of rolling into wound cells. PVDF-based films with Cyrene and Tamisolve demonstrated excellent adhesion to electrode materials, ensuring a stable and uniform coating. However, PVDF-based films exhibited more pronounced cracking during the bending test compared to those made with PVP, as visible in SEM images in Fig. 4g-k. Such adhesion and cracking behavior reflects potential challenges during roll-to-roll coating or calendaring, where mechanical stress and layer uniformity are decisive for industrial scalability. Additionally, the PVDF-Cy sample was subjected to 100 bending cycles to evaluate film adhesion and resistance. The resistance measured before bending was 125–230 Ω cm⁻¹, and after 100 bends 145–359 Ω cm⁻¹, confirming good mechanical integrity and minimal effect on resistance (Fig. S12). In contrast, the PVP-Cy film displayed superior cohesion during bending, with little to no cracks, highlighting its suitability for practical applications (Fig. 4d, j). These findings emphasize the promise of Cyrene and Tamisolve as environmentally friendly solvents for developing high-performance bendable supercapacitors suitable for industrial use.

While bending tests provide a basic measure of electrode film integrity, we extend this with an evaluation of film adhesion to the substrate, a rarely tested but industrially crucial parameter. Modified tape test adopted from the ASTM D3359 [44] standard was used to evaluate adhesion of electrode films to the current collector as well as the cohesion of the electrode film itself. In practice, this is assessed using a grid test (Fig. 5), which evaluates film adhesion by cutting the film into a grid pattern and applying adhesive tape to peel off the resulting square sections. PVDF-NMP showed sufficient adhesion but poor cohesion, as evidenced by significant material removal with 0.8 N cm⁻¹ tape and a high number of peeled-off residues (Fig. 5a inset). The introduction of Cyrene in electrode preparation led to a notable improvement in both adhesion and cohesion properties, as demonstrated in Fig. 5b and c. Even at exceptionally high mass loading, the material remained firmly attached after peeling off with a strong tape (10.6 N cm⁻¹). While the

Fig. 3. (a) GCD profiles of SC-GN3 mixtures at 1 A g⁻¹. Combination of PVDF-Cy (red), PVP-Cy (yellow), PVP-NMP (violet), PVDF-NMP (green), PVDF-Tamisolve (blue). (b) Cyclic voltammograms profiles at 100 mV s⁻¹. (c) Nyquist plot with close-up inset. (d) Cyclic stability for 100,000 cycles at 10 A g⁻¹ (right) with Coulombic efficiency (left).

Fig. 4. Bending test around stainless-steel rod. The width of each film is >1 cm. (a) PVDF-NMP, (b) PVDF-Tam, (c) PVDF-Cy, (d) PVP-Cy, (e) PVP-NMP, (f) PVP-Tam free-standing film. SEM images of films were taken during the bending position: (g) PVDF-NMP, (h) PVDF-Tam, (i) PVDF-Cy, (j) PVP-Cy, (k) PVP-NMP.

previously published report [7], examined films on bare Al-foil, the present study focuses on C-Al foil. C-Al foil was used because it is the industry standard and provides significantly better adhesion for carbon-based electrodes. Films prepared on C-Al foil using Cyrene exhibited excellent adhesion.

This mechanical robustness suggests excellent conditions for

winding of wound sections for cylindrical cell form factors. While the PVP-Cy system demonstrated superb bending flexibility, its adhesion to the substrate was relatively weak (Fig. 5e). Nonetheless, this formulation remains promising for applications such as pouch cells or wearable electronics, where mechanical strain is lower and flexibility is a priority, emphasizing the superior mechanical integrity of electrodes fabricated

Fig. 5. Grid test with subsequent application of adhesion tapes with defined adhesion force. 4 tapes were applied in the same order for every sample. (a) PVDF-NMP, (b) PVDF-Tam, (c) PVDF-Cy, (d) PVP-NMP, (e) PVP-Cy. Tapes were used on every sample in the same order as follows: 0.8 N cm^{-1} , 1.15 N cm^{-1} , 2.6 N cm^{-1} , 10.6 N cm^{-1} . Insets: The used adhesion tape shows residues of the removed electrode film.

with green solvents, particularly Cyrene. The improved performance showcases their potential as excellent alternatives to conventional NMP-based formulations. Full grid test images for all the combinations are provided in the SI (Fig. S13). The combination of both methods, bending test around a stainless-steel rod and tape test adopted from the ASTM D3359, provides a practical and robust framework for assessing electrode mechanical integrity. Importantly, both methods require minimal specialized equipment for practical use in an electrode fabrication laboratory. Overall, PVP exhibited slightly reduced energy and power density as well as limited cyclic stability, although it remains the more environmentally friendly option. In terms of mechanical behavior, PVP-based electrodes showed fewer cracks during bending but demonstrated weaker adhesion to the C–Al substrate.

4. Conclusion

As sustainable energy storage gains priority, replacing hazardous solvents such as NMP is essential. This study presents Cyrene and Tamsolve as green alternatives that maintain high electrochemical performance while improving environmental compatibility. Alongside, we also included PVP as a common non-fluorinated binder with a more environmentally benign profile. Electrodes fabricated with PVDF-Cy delivered the highest capacitance (152 F g^{-1} at 1 A g^{-1}), low ESR (6.9Ω), excellent long-term stability (91 % retention after 100,000 cycles), and competitive energy density of 66.6 Wh kg^{-1} with a power density of 1.85 kW kg^{-1} , surpassing the traditional PVDF-NMP system. Another important achievement of this study is the successful fabrication of high-mass-loading electrodes ($>6 \text{ mg cm}^{-2}$) while maintaining strong adhesion to the substrate, which is an essential but often overlooked factor in industrially relevant conditions. Mechanical testing, including bending and adhesion assessments, revealed that PVDF-Tam and PVDF-Cy electrodes exhibit strong cohesion and adhesion, critical for winding in the cylindrical cell fabrication process. Overall, these results validate Cyrene and Tamsolve as viable, sustainable alternatives to NMP for the fabrication of high-performance, mechanically robust supercapacitor electrodes. Their compatibility with fluorinated PVDF and non-fluorinated PVP binders, combined with superior film uniformity and electrochemical stability, positions them as strong candidates for scalable applications. These findings bridge the gap between laboratory-scale and industrial fabrication. By integrating Tamsolve and Cyrene as green solvents and PVP as a non-fluorinated binder, this study provides a route toward the next generation of sustainable, high-performance supercapacitors for industrial applications.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Ivan Dědek: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Vojtěch Kupka:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Veronika Šedajová:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. **Petr Jakubec:** Writing – original draft. **Matej Navrátil:** Methodology, Investigation. **Michal Otyepka:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Resources, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: M.O. and V.Š. have a share in ATOMIVER, s.r.o. (Czechia) focused on the development of supercapacitor electrode materials, including SC-GN3. Other authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the European Union's Horizon Europe EIC Transition project Trans2Dchem (No. 101057616), furthermore by ERDF/ESF project TECHSCALE (No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004587). We also acknowledge financial support of the Research Infrastructure NanoEnviCz, supported by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic under Project No. LM2023066. M.O. also acknowledges financial support of the European Union under the REFRESH – Research Excellence For Region Sustainability and High-tech Industries project number CZ.10.03.01/00/22_003/0000048 via the Operational Programme Just Transition.

The authors used Artificial Intelligence language models only to improve the clarity and fluency of the manuscript. The authors carefully edited the content afterwards.

The authors gratefully thank Eirini Ioannou (SEM), Jan Pauswang (electrochemistry), Emil Remeslníček (sample preparation) and Gifty Jacob (sample preparation), Martin Pykal for the help with graphics.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2025.172220>.

Data availability

Data are available via ZENODO repository at: <https://zenodo.org/records/18089032>

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